

The model of the dimension

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Abstracts

As we all know, our universe has three dimensions. These three dimensions are equivalent, and they can be converted to each other. Dimensions have directions and infinite length. There are only two states of a dimension: presence or absence. We believe that the n -dimensional space ($n \geq 0, n \in \mathbb{Z}$) contains at most n dimensions in the $n+m$ space ($m \in \mathbb{N}$), but cannot contain all $n+m$ dimensions. Therefore, we consider that three-dimensional space does not contain dimensions greater than 3.

Text

1. Known dimensions and their properties

- a. Equivalence: The three known dimensions are completely equivalent and indistinguishable.
- b. Interchangeability: They are interchangeable.
- c. They extend indefinitely in the determined direction.
- d. They have only two states: presence or non-existence.

2. Depending on the nature of the dimension, we can draw the following conclusions:

The n -dimensional space ($n \geq 0, n \in \mathbb{Z}$) contains at most n dimensions in the $n+m$ space ($m \in \mathbb{N}$), but cannot contain all $n+m$ dimensions. This point has nothing to do with size. Example: A very long line cannot contain a complete triangle, even if the triangle is small, the line can contain at most part of the triangle. Figure 1

Figure 1

Conclusion

We consider that there are at most 3 complete dimensions in 3D space, and no complete extra dimensions.

Discussion

How to cram extra dimensions into three-dimensional space.

If we use 1 to indicate that the dimension exists and 0 to indicate that the dimension does not exist, then the space can be expressed as:

Zero dimension: $0+0+0$

One-dimensional: $1+0+0$

Two-dimensional: $1+1+0$

Three-dimensional: $1+1+1$

11 dimensions: $1+1+1 +1+1+1+1 +1+1+1+1$

The first method crams 11 dimensions into 3 dimensions: $1+1+1 +0+0+0+0 +0+0+0+0$. But this result gives a new three-dimensional, and the original 11-dimensional disappears. Another method is to use "quasi-dimensional" with limited size. But "quasi-dimensional" is only a subset of dimensions, just as dogs are a subset of animals. Obviously, this solution does not really solve the problem.

If no extra dimension exists, how do we explain those interesting questions? For example, what are the basic units of the world, the vanishing gravity, and so on. We actually found another way: density interpretation of wave functions.